

Locating Sree Sree Thakur Anukul Chandra's Ideologies within the Indian National Movement

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Abstract:

Very few movement that dot the landscape of our nation have thrived as well as expanded as extensively as the Satsang Movement started by spiritual Guru, Sree Sree Thakur Anukul Chandra in the early twentieth century. Colonial India witnessed the evolution of many spiritual movements parallel to the ongoing national movement which shared visions of developing and unifying India. The ideologies of Thakur Anukul Chandra deeply influenced many nationalist leaders during the national building process. He looked upon spirituality as the point of convergence for all diverse religious forces in India capable of unifying India into a national current. Who was Anukul Chandra? What were the ideologies of Thakur Anukul Chandra? How did his ideologies and principles inspire the national leaders? How was the national movement influenced and shaped by the teachings of Thakur Anukul Chandra? The following article is an attempt to answer the following questions.

Keywords: spirituality, nation-making, non-violence, dharma, ideology, freedom struggle.

Introduction:

Society is a comprehensive human organization, where relationship of togetherness and co-operation emerges and develops among human beings as they live together. Nineteenth and twentieth century was the time when spiritual awakening rose through various socio-cultural movements. Ideologies of the socio-cultural movements which emerged during this period greatly influenced in shaping the Indian national movement. Our freedom struggle was not only about removing Britishers from the Indian soil, but was also about making India a better place, about unifying people of diverse culture into one nation, about uplifting masses from poverty, about building better humans and about overall social, economic, political and cultural development. A better society, which was so indispensable to humans was, thus, to be restructured. These tasks were undertaken not only by nationalist leaders but also by spiritual leaders. One such often neglected or rarely researched upon spiritual leader is Sree Sree Thakur Anukul Chandra. .

The ideologies of Thakur Anukul Chandra deeply influenced many nationalist leaders during the national building process. He looked upon spirituality as the point of convergence for all diverse religious forces in India capable of unifying India into a national current. The growth of social organisations and social relations were integrated in his ideology.¹ Who was Anukul Chandra? What were the ideologies of Thakur Anukul Chandra? How did his ideologies and principles inspire the national leaders? How was the national movement influenced and shaped by the teachings of Thakur Anukul Chandra? The following article is an attempt to answer the following questions.

Thakur Anukul Chandra- The Spiritual Guru:

Sree Sree Thakur Anukul Chandra, a physician, a spiritual guru and the founder of

Satsang Ashram was born in Himaitpur, a village in Pabna district of present day Bangladesh. Born into a Brahmin family of Sri Shivchandra Chakraborty and Srimati Manmohini Devi on the 14th of September 1888², Anukul Chandra was regarded as a Yuga- Purushottama by his devotees. Being born in such a remote area, he saw hardship of masses at the grass root level from a very early age. With his deep sense of curiosity and a superb capacity for keen observation, he was believed to be able to understand concepts clearly and identify their basic origins. Moreover, he was known to be blessed with naturally curious and scientific mindset that would explore further into the root of problems. He had a keen understanding of the truth of things and a strong common sense at a younger age. He had a great love for his family.

Anukul Chandra began his formal education at Himaitpur village elementary school in 1893. In 1898, he was admitted to Pabna Institute where he studied upto 8th grade and later attended Naihati High school in the 24 Parganas of West Bengal until 1905. Anukul Chandra Thakur then completed a diploma in Homeopathy from National Medical College of Calcutta³. He was fond of writing and wrote many short plays, songs and poems, the first in 1905. His songs and poems were published in a book, '*Debjani-O-Anyanya*'. During his last days, Thakur conveyed his guiding principles for life to one of his friends Atulchandra Bhattacharya, which was compiled in the famous book '*Satyanusaran*' (*The Pursuit of Truth*) in 1918. Anukul Chandra tied knot with his first wife Soroshibala in 1906 and with his second Sarbamangala later in life.

With the help of his mother, Thakur Anukul Chandra formed the *kirtan* group which attracted people from different strata of society. He gradually gained fame as a physician, spiritual guru, teacher and a guide. Steadily Thakur's social

movement took the name of Satsang. Satsang was originally registered in Pabna as a public charitable institution in 1925. After partition it was re-registered in 1951 when Thakur Anukul Chandra shifted from Pabna to Devghar on 2nd September 1946. Later Satsang was registered as a society under the Indian Societies Registration Act 1860.

Over the years many philanthropic activities were included like the Vishwa Bigyan Kendra, Satsang Chemical Works where medicines are manufactured, The Satsang Press and Satsang Publishing House. The habitation and working of these institutions are run by the member themselves. Also the Tapovan School and Matrividyalya imparts education to the masses. His ashram developed into a sprawling complex housing a science lab, charitable hospital, academic institute, a printing unit, community kitchen and an administrative building. Sri Sri Thakur Anukul Chandra left his mortal frame on 27th January 1969 after which this spiritual movement was carried forward by his followers.

Even after so many years of its initiation, Satsang is expanding and spreading worldwide. Presently, it has more than two thousand branches worldwide in India, Bangladesh, Burma, Europe and America. Satsang Vihars or 'Thakurbaaris' have been set up in different parts of India. Many eminent national leaders and personalities met Anukul Chandra and were inspired by his thoughts like Mahatma Gandhi, Deshbandhu Chittaranjan Das, Dr. Rajendra Prasad, Shubhas Chandra Bose, Lal Bahadur Shastri, Sarat Chandra Chatterjee, Fazlul Haq, Swami Abhedananda, Acharya Tulsi and Dr. Shyamaprasad Mukherjee.

Ideologies Of Thakur Anukul Chandra :

Sri Sri Thakur Anukul Chandra enlightened people with his mindful thoughts and ideas on society, religion, state government, politics, law, etc. He said the element of society is created as soon as two people come to know each other. For a good social order he defined the formula as- "He who lives under one command leads into the society"⁴. He excluded from the society the unorganized relations in definite associations.⁵ According to his ideas an ideal man must establish himself in a surrounding environment through his real life service, contact and sympathy.⁶ Sri Sri Thakur said that the ideal of man has to be the promoter of the being towards perfection. He has to be the epitome of love, compassion, sympathy, service and all such divine virtues and qualities. An ideal man is the one who not only feels every being and thing to be an integral part of his own self, but even demonstrates that in his own conduct.⁷ Anukul Chandra extensively focused on creating humans of good character and building a better society. He clearly laid out the rules for a compatible marriage based upon eugenic principles of nature, which were

to be followed for bringing better progeny of a heedful, benevolent, concentric and honest nature.⁸ He asked every individual to infuse 'dharma' into their lives. This saint said dharma is the one that nurtures our life and growth. Hence, dharma is one, but there appears difference of opinions among distinct religious sets regarding the concept of dharma.⁹ Throwing light upon the worldly desires, he expressed that the problems in life arise due to the want of 'peace and happiness'.¹⁰ He carried the belief that peace and happiness could be achieved in human life through the attainment of truth and goodness.¹¹ If an individual desires to perform his activities in an evil way then the person is subjected to sorrows and sufferings and if directed otherwise, is subjected to peace and happiness.¹²

Interaction Of Thakur Anukul Chandra With Different National Leaders

Sri Sri Thakur Anukul Chandra played a very important role in the Indian National Movement through 'spiritual awakening' among the masses. He advised people to follow the correct path of dharma to attain freedom. He believed that India could only attain freedom by building humans of good character and that we must start with man making program. Through his mindful thoughts and teachings he inspired a number of national leaders and motivated the latter to move forward in shaping the freedom struggle movement. The following paper will reveal some interactions between Thakur Anukul Chandra and some nationalist leaders.

Mahatma Gandhi, after being deeply influenced by the devotion of Deshbandhu Chittaranjan Das, a great freedom fighter and disciple of Thakur Anukul Chandra, decided to meet Anukul Chandra. Gandhiji was tremendously enchanted by him. Out of curiosity to meet such a finest man, Mahatma Gandhi reached the ashram of Pabna, Hemaaitpur on 23rd Mat 1925 to meet this spiritual guru. He was accompanied by Lord Anukul, mother Manomohini and other devotees. Although the discussion between them could not happen satisfactorily, Gandhi was inspired enough to say that Thakur had given a practical shape to his thoughts about a developed village which he had envisioned.¹³ Mahatma Gandhi was moved by Anukul Chandra's mission to reform the society with universal ethics and therefore, again met him in Kolkata later when Gandhiji heard news of Thakur's illness.

Deshbandhu Chittaranjan Das was a disciple and a great devotee of Shree Shree Thakur Anukul Chandra. He learnt the value of truth from his spiritual guide in all his dealings. In carrying forward his fight for India's independence, Chittaranjan Das believed that Thakur gave him the strength he did not possess before and began to see things clearly.

Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose met Thakur Anukul Chandra after qualifying his I.C.S. exam. Netaji's

parents were disciples of Thakur. Subhash Bose met Anukul Chandra at Pabna Ashram and asked him as to “where should we start for giving the real service to our nation?” His reply emphasized on the man-making programme and gave the concept of compatible marriage.

Similarly, **Dr. Shyama Prasad Mukherjee’s** interaction with Thakur Anukul Chandra answered his quest to find a solution to the harmonious co-habilitation of different sects in the nation-building process.¹⁴

Locating Thakur Anukul Chandra’s Ideologies In The Indian National Movement

Indian national movement was a long drawn conflict against the britishers envisioning a independent, democratic and secular country with overall socio-economic development. The ideologies of Shree Shree Thakur Anukul Chandra greatly influenced in shaping and structuring the Indian National Movement. Thakur Anukul Chandra taught people to be courageous and fight against one’s own weakness firstly as weakness is the living image of sin. He awakened the masses through his mindful thoughts which inspired them to join various mass movements. He encouraged every individual to be self-confident and courageous, to unite mind and face, acquire strength and enter the path of Dharma. The non-violent satyagraha movement could also have been influenced by such ideologies because Thakur also talked about the degeneration of society that had occurred over centuries and to reform the society by forgetting sectarian violence and making for the future welfare of the people.

Thus, to conclude with, Sree Sree Thakur Anukul Chandra was one such holy spiritual guru who greatly contributed in shaping the Indian National Movement through his ideologies and principles. With his advice on removing one’s own weakness and gaining self-confidence, with his vision of inculcating man-making programme and eliminating sectarian violence, we could successfully achieve India’s freedom.

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